

University of technology,
Fatehpuria main road,
post kumhariawas,vatikaroad,
jaipur (RJ) , Jaipur 303905

Social and Economic Problems Faced by Women Vendors in doing Clothing Business

PhD scholar - preeti yadav

University of technology jaipur (Rajasthan)

Summary -

The objective of the research paper is to study the Economic and social problems faced by women vendors of **Mahendragarh district in Hariyana in doing the business of clothes.** When a woman vendor sells

clothes, she has to face numerous problems. Being uneducated, financial constraints, selling her clothes in the weekly market by putting up a cart, selling clothes by standing in the hot sun, attracting the people by shouting etc. are some of the difficulties. Buying the goods and selling the collected goods (clothes) is a big challenge. The women buyers also argue with the selling women, compete with them, harass them and exploit them. Due to their lack of education, all these differences and disputes are done with them. Being weak in mathematics, they also face difficulties in collecting money. Due to the availability of goods (clothes) at high prices according to fashion and interest, the women vendors are not able to buy the goods (clothes) at high prices. This affects her market. The women vendors have to face extreme difficulties, which I am trying to find out.

Key words -

Problems, Losses, Risks, Disputes, Competition faced by Women Sellers

Introduction -

In this paper **Narnaul tehsil of Mahendragarh district in Haryana, India** and the surrounding villages have been included. I have observed that uneducated women face problems in online shopping, due to which they prefer to buy goods (clothes) from the market themselves but when they encounter an uneducated female seller, then both sides face problems. Due to the illiteracy of the female seller, due to lack of knowledge, the educated women exploit them. The educated and clever women want to extort clothes from them at a lower price, which is creating social problems. And if we talk about the economic problem, which has become a common problem in today's era, due to financial constraints, the women seller take money on loan for selling and storing her goods, and due to not being able to pay back, she leads to greater loss.

Objective -

My aim is to find out the important aspects which are creating problem to women seller in selling garments, like lack of quality, lack of quantity, lack of reputation, risk and loss etc, we have to find out the difficulties which we have to face.

Research Methodology -

I have collected descriptive data on online and offline shopping of women vendors in which some women parties say that there are many problems in this regard.

I have collected 300 data and evaluated it using rating scale in which I have observed which problems are more prevalent.

Graph -

I have explained the data by making graphs and pictures in which the explanation has been done through economic and social problems. I have collected the information by doing offline survey using T test. And the data has been designed by explaining through pictures.

Direction -

I have explained the data through graphs in which social and economic problems have been explained through tables.

Questionnaire -

Question 1) What are the problems in selling clothes?

- 1) Bargaining 2) Hawking 3) Reasonable price 4) All of the above

Answer - **All of the above**

Question 2) Which is the most popular dress in Madhya Pradesh?

- 1) Saree 2) Suit 3) Rajputani 4) All of the above

Answer - **All of the above**

Question 3) Which clothes are not accepted by the society?

- 1) Short clothes
- 2) Clothes with open sleeves
- 3) Clothes without dupatta
- 4) All of the above

Answer - **All of the above**

Result -

As a result, financial crisis including not getting loan on time and social problems like conservatism, superstition, wrong mentality, child marriage are still prevalent. In the interest of society, women are prohibited from wearing clothes according to their choice. If we talk about Dhar district of Madhya Pradesh, even today women have to face the practice of veil, they cannot show their face to any man. Due to which women can only wear saree as clothing. Due to which both women sellers and customers have to face problems. Whether they are married or unmarried, they are mostly wearing saree. If the young generation does business, then women sellers will never be able to expand their business because there is no profit.

Hypothesis –

I have imagined zero to top in the calculation because in **Mahendragarh district of Haryana**. women are left with only a small amount of clothes after selling sarees. They buy all the clothes that can be sold socially and earn some profit by selling them.

Conclusion –

This shows that traditional rules have more importance in **Mahendragarh district**, due to which even today women do not have freedom, they are only being made superstitious, they are allowed to wear only those clothes which are in vogue. Due to which there is financial crisis in the society as well as lack of outside customers due to non-availability of clothes as per the requirement, because the culture and civilization, history, clothing etc. of all the cities or villages are not the same. At some places there is more demand for Patiala suit, while at some places Rajputani clothes are worn, which is not available with the female seller of **Mahendragarh district of Haryana**, due to being in small towns she is not able to earn much income. Therefore my objective is that there is an urgent need to make people aware first of all through online and offline so that social welfare can be done.

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